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Executive Summary

Ocean conservation efforts have historically overlooked Equity and Environmental Justice (EEJ) principles, despite gaining attention in land-based conservation. EEJ emphasizes fair distribution of environmental benefits, elimination of social and environmental inequities, and addressing disparities, especially in underserved communities. Neglecting EEJ in ocean conservation can worsen environmental health disparities, hinder community resilience, and complicate the integration of EEJ with biodiversity conservation priorities.

The field of EEJ is complex, with distributive, procedural, and recognition justice forming its core dimensions. Emerging in response to environmental inequalities, EEJ aims to eliminate social and environmental disparities by ensuring equitable access to resources, strengthening ecosystems, and engaging communities in conservation. Access to nature is crucial for public health, but disparities exist, with communities of color facing limited access. Tailoring

initiatives to diverse needs involves addressing specific accommodations, such as sign language interpreters and improved accessibility in national parks. An in-depth examination, commitment to dismantling systemic barriers, and promotion of collaborative governance models are essential for fostering an inclusive and equitable environment. Direct engagement with indigenous and underrepresented communities is recommended, ensuring their participation in decision-making processes. Collaborative governance involving diverse stakeholders can lead to more equitable outcomes in Marine Protected Area establishment and management.

List of Acronyms

BLM: Bureau of Land Management

BOEM: Bureau of Ocean Energy Management, U.S. Department of the Interior

CCA: California Coastal Act of 1976

CINMS: Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

DOC: U.S. Department of Commerce

DOI: U.S. Department of the Interior

EEJ : Equity and Environmental Justice

EJ: Environmental Justice

EPA: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency

EO: Executive Order

MPAs: Marine Protected Areas

NMSs: National Marine Sanctuaries

NMFS: National Marine Fisheries Service, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

NOAA: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Department of Commerce

NPS: National Park Service, U.S. Department of the Interior

COPC: California Ocean Protection Council

OCAP: Ocean Climate Action Plan

OJS: Ocean Justice Strategy

ONMS: Office of National Marine Sanctuaries, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

OPC: Ocean Policy Committee

SMCAs-ER: State Marine Conservation Areas for Educational and Research Purposes

SMRs: State Marine Reserves

SMPs: State Marine Parks

SMRMAs: State Marine Recreational Management Areas

USDA: United States Department of Agriculture

USFS: United States Forest Service; United States Department of Agriculture

Definitions

Environmental Health Disparities¹:

Environmental health disparities arise from the interaction of poor environmental quality and social inequities in communities where individuals live, work, learn, and play. These disparities manifest as variations in health outcomes and disease prevalence stemming from the unequal distribution of environmental burdens and social determinants of health, including differences in individual behaviors, cultural influences, access to health services, economic status, and literacy levels. The existence of environmental health disparities underscores the need for concerted efforts to address both environmental quality and social inequalities, aiming to achieve fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all individuals, irrespective of race, nationality, or income, in environmental laws and policies.

Environmental Justice^{2 3} (EJ): The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, irrespective of race, color, gender, sexual orientation, national origin, tribal affiliation, religion, disability, or income during the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies. This includes but is not limited to;

- equitable protection from environmental and health hazards,
- access to a healthy and sustainable environment, and
- participation in decision-making processes for underserved communities.

Equity^{4 5 6}: The consistent and systematic fair, just, and impartial treatment of all individuals, including those from underserved communities historically denied such treatment.

Meaningful Involvement: Communities have the opportunity to participate in decisions affecting their environment and health. Their contributions inform NOAA Fisheries' decisions, and community concerns are considered in the decision-making process. Decision-makers actively seek and facilitate the involvement of those potentially affected.

¹ Informed by [National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences](#).

² Informed by [Learn About Environmental Justice | US EPA](#)

³ Informed by [First National People of Color Environmental Leadership Summit Principles of Environmental Justice](#)

⁴ As defined by [EO 13985](#) and [EO 14091](#).

⁵ Informed by [First National People of Color Environmental Leadership Summit Principles of Environmental Justice](#).

⁶ Informed by [Bennett et al., 2021. Blue growth and blue justice: Ten risks and solutions for the ocean economy. Marine Policy, 125.](#)

Underserved Communities⁷: Communities systematically denied full opportunities to participate in economic, social, and civic life, including but not limited to women and girls; Black, Latino, and Indigenous and Native American persons; Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders; LGBTQ+ persons; persons with disabilities; persons in rural or urban areas; and those adversely affected by persistent poverty or inequality. Identification and meaningful involvement with underserved communities are regionally specific and an ongoing, region-specific, long-term commitment.

Climate Change: The long-term shift in oceanic and atmospheric conditions resulting in increased temperature, heat waves, sea level rise, and changes in weather patterns. Climate justice seeks to protect the rights of those most vulnerable to the effects of climate change, recognizing historical marginalization and overburdening of disadvantaged communities.

Recognitional Justice: Acknowledgement and respect for pre-existing governance arrangements, distinct rights, worldviews, knowledge, needs, livelihoods, histories, and cultures of different groups in decisions.

Procedural Justice⁸: The level of participation and inclusiveness of decision-making and the quality of governance processes.

Recognitional justice⁹: The acknowledgment of and respect for pre-existing governance arrangements as well as the distinct rights, worldviews, knowledge, needs, livelihoods, histories, and cultures of different groups in decisions.

Distributive Justice¹⁰: The equitable allocation and distribution of resources and benefits among diverse demographic groups.

Disadvantaged Communities^{11 12}: “Disadvantaged communities are those that are marginalized, underserved, and overburdened by pollution. The beta version of the Climate and Economic Justice Screening Tool (CEJST) uses a methodology and datasets that identify communities that are economically disadvantaged and overburdened by pollution and underinvestment in housing, transportation, water and wastewater infrastructure, and health care. A community qualifies as “disadvantaged” if the census tract is above the threshold for one or more environmental or climate indicators and the tract is above the threshold for the socioeconomic indicators.”

⁷ As defined by [EO 13985](#)

⁸ Informed by Bennett et al., 2021. Blue growth and blue justice: Ten risks and solutions for the ocean economy. Marine Policy, 125.

⁹ Informed by Bennett et al., 2021. Blue growth and blue justice: Ten risks and solutions for the ocean economy. Marine Policy, 125. ¹³ Informed by Bennett et al., 2021. Blue growth and blue justice: Ten risks and solutions for the ocean economy. Marine Policy, 125.

¹⁰ Informed by Lamont, Julian and Christi Favor, "Distributive Justice", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2017 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.)

¹¹ As informed by “The White House’s [Climate and Economic Justice Screening Tool: Frequently Asked Questions](#)”.

¹² As informed by [Executive Order 14008](#).

Inclusive and Equitable Environment: The establishment of a fair and welcoming space that accommodates the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders, irrespective of their background or identity.

Introduction

Incorporating Equity and Environmental Justice (EEJ) principles into land-based conservation efforts has been a growing concern for policymakers, managers, and communities. However, the same attention has not been directed toward oceans. Environmental justice, emerging in response to environmental inequalities faced by underserved communities, is a concept rooted in the inequitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens across all segments of society (Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Bennett, 2022; Bennett, 2018; Bennett, 2022; Martin, 2019; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Parsons, 2021; Jones, 2009; Floyd, 1999; Blount, 2007; NOAA, 2023; OPC, 2022; Lau, 2021; Christensen & King, 2017; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Reineman, 2016; Mascia, 2010; Scott, 2013; Newson, 2022; Garcia, 2017; Landau, 2020). EEJ emphasizes principles of equity, participation, and recognition for all members of society (Mohai, 2009; Bullard, 2001; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Scott, 2013; Christensen & King, 2017; NOAA, 2023; OPC, 2022). This discipline focuses on identifying and eliminating the social and environmental inequities between underserved communities and the more privileged parts of society (e.g., communities with lower vs. higher wealth, education, and social advantages). Underserved communities, in this context, refer to groups that have historically experienced disproportionate environmental and social disparities, often due to factors such as lower wealth, education, and social advantages (Executive Order 14096, 2021; OPC, 2022; NOAA, 2022; Newson, 2022; Bennett, 2023).

Attention by the EEJ community to harm has historically focused on the unequal distribution of the health burdens caused by exposure to pollution from the agriculture industry, urbanization, or industrial practices (Bennett, 2023; Martin, 2019; Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992). For example, many EEJ case studies focus on the widespread practice of placing toxic industries (e.g., coal power plants, oil refineries, and factories) in or adjacent to underserved communities (Bennett, 2023; Martin, 2019; Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992). Such biased exposure to toxins leads to a higher risk of cancer and a lower quality of life for adjacent communities than other members of society (South, 2018; Mohai, 2009; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Pellow, 2018; Bullard, 2001).

Systematic inequalities between communities encompass persistent structural disparities in societies, perpetuated by policies, institutions, and social norms, notably in economic, racial, and gender disparities (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2023). Such inequalities are deeply entrenched in society, affecting access to resources and opportunities and the distribution of burdens for different groups of people. Policies wield significant influence over resource, opportunity, and burden distribution, either exacerbating or mitigating inequalities based on design and implementation (Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Agyeman & Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018). For example, the funding requirements imposed by financial institutions (e.g., for mortgages) can disproportionately burden specific communities, thereby perpetuating economic and other disparities. Historically, racial discrimination in housing loans (i.e., redlining) and

exclusionary zoning (and rezoning) has been a subtle form of using government authority and power to foster and perpetuate discriminatory practices ([Mizutani, 2019](#); [Jackson, 2021](#); Bullard, 2001). For example, when zoning policies prioritize commercial development over the creation of affordable housing, they contribute to gentrification and limit the availability of essential amenities (Bullard, 2001; [Mizutani, 2019](#); [Jackson, 2021](#)). Systematic barriers frequently trace their roots to historical injustices, discriminatory policies, or entrenched societal prejudices, all hindering equitable access to resources and services (Bullard, 2001; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Pellow, 2018; Mohai, 1992; [Mizutani, 2019](#); [Jackson, 2021](#)).

Systematic barriers span many dimensions of society and include environmental injustice and racial inequity (Bullard, 2001). Environmental injustice manifests when marginalized communities bear disproportionate pollution and environmental hazards, often due to discriminatory policies and industry practices (Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009). Racial inequity permeates various aspects of society, from education to healthcare, with deep-rooted structural biases that disadvantage racial minority groups. Policies are key to addressing these disparities, as they significantly shape burden and barrier distribution (Bullard, 2001).

There is now a recognition that in addition to the harm that comes from exposure to toxins, harm derives from other negative experiences and systemic barriers, including those that prevent specific communities from accessing beneficial natural spaces and other environmental resources ([Agyeman & Bullard, 2002](#)). Consequently, EEJ discussions have evolved from an early, narrow focus on reducing environmental harms to a broader perspective that emphasizes the promotion of equity in the access of all people to environmental benefits. Such beneficial resources include high-quality natural environments, such as National Parks and coastlines, and healthy environmental conditions, such as the water quality in areas that subsistence fishers rely on for their activities. Examples of how systemic barriers prevent environmental equity include unequal access to green spaces in urban spaces (Scott, 2013), disparities in funding for parks and recreation facilities in marginalized communities (Floyd, 1999; Garcia, 2017; Scott, 2013), limited access to federal activities, processes and documents (OJS, OPC 2023) and limited transportation options to reach natural areas (Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017).

The concentration of poverty and affluence has resulted in a 2-tier system of publicly funded park and recreation provision in the US (Scott, 2013). This has created a situation where wealthier communities enjoy superior funding, leading to higher-quality amenities (Scott, 2013; Garcia, 2018). Simultaneously, inner cities and poorer communities experience a deficit in basic funding and historical access to such natural resources, contributing to an enduring imbalance in recreational opportunities (Scott, 2013; Garcia, 2017). The deficit in access to parks qualifies communities as “park poor,” a term defined by California law as having less than three acres of parks per thousand residents and being income poor with a median household income below \$47,331 (Garcia, 2017). Whereas many park-poor areas are situated in low-income communities inhabited by underserved communities, including ethnic and racial minorities (Taylor et al., 2007; Scott, 2013) and civil rights (Garcia, 2013; Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018) issues. The

unequal distribution of green spaces in urban areas has an impact on residents' well-being (South, 2018; Jaffe, 2015; Wang, 2005; Rowland-Shea, 2020). In contrast, equal distribution of green areas contributes to healthier ecosystems and fosters stronger community bonds (South, 2018; Jaffe, 2015; Wang, 2005; Rowland-Shea, 2020).

To participate in federal activities, underserved communities may face barriers such as the need for time, transportation, childcare, and access to technology (OJS, OPC 2023; Bennett, 2021). Time, transportation, money, childcare, and access to technology is needed to participate in federal activities, which can be a barrier to underserved communities (OJS, OPC, 2023; OCAP, OPC, 2023). This can result in a disproportionate burden on individuals within these communities. Attending federal processes may require missing a day of work or foregoing pay, unlike federal employees who are compensated for their attendance (OJS, OPC 2023; Bennett et al, 2023; Bennett et al, 2018).

In the case of California, the lack of equitable public transportation to coastal areas and national parks contributes to disparities in the enjoyment of natural resources and open spaces. Despite the California Coastal Act (CCA) passed in 1976, which aims to protect public coastal access for all residents, significant barriers persist (Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017). White, affluent, and senior Californians are found to live in closer proximity to public coastal access points and have been found to obstruct public access to beaches unlawfully (Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017). Whereas underserved communities are found to reside farther from coastal access points and national parks which results in extended travel distances. The higher travel costs from longer distances exacerbate the burden and inherent inequities in the distribution of public access points, including coastal areas and national parks (Christensen, 2017; Floyd, 1999; Reineman, 2016). Housing in coastal areas tends to be unaffordable, further contributing to systemic barriers and pushing less wealthy individuals towards inland Central California, further away from coastal areas and national parks (Reineman, 2016; Scott, 2013; Christensen, 2017). The inequitable geographic discrepancy has notable implications for EEJ in terms of access to public open space and natural places (Reineman, 2016; Scott, 2013; Christensen, 2017). The failure to uphold EEJ goals within policies perpetuates social and environmental injustices, impeding both community well-being and ecosystem health (Reineman, 2016; Scott, 2013; Christensen, 2017). This spans from the unequal distribution of green spaces to the sustainable management of coastal areas.

The contrast between EEJ and biodiversity conservation often underscores differing priorities and approaches. There is an absence of unanimous agreement among different stakeholder groups about what constitutes the right thing to do, causing the persistent lack of consensus in biodiversity conservation (Martin, 2017; Folchi, 2019). Historically, the conservation field has featured a dichotomy between 'environmentalism of the poor'¹³ and

¹³ “the environmentalism of the poor, defence of the environment, far from being motivated by abstract ideals or sentiments towards the environment or nature, constitutes a response on the part of the poor—primarily the indigenous and peasant populations of the global South—to a wholly tangible and entirely materialistic situation: the deterioration of the environment in which they live and the consequent impossibility of subsistence.” (Folchi, 2019)

'Western environmentalism'¹⁴. These 'poor environmentalists' often place everything at stake in their attempts to prevent the exploitation of their natural resources and resist pollution (Martin, 2017; Folchi, 2019). Environmentalism of the poor is often motivated by protecting commodity frontiers in developing countries from extractive capital, as exemplified by local farmers in places like India, often putting their lives at stakes such as chaining themselves to trees (Martin, 2017; Jouffray, 2020; Vinyeta, 2016). At the same time, western environmentalism tends to emphasize biodiversity preservation, and ecosystem services for its perceived purity of wilderness and use to humans (Martin, 2017; Folchi, 2019). The diverse motivations extend to the core of conservation efforts, with some focusing on practical human welfare, while others draw inspiration from spiritual connections to the natural world (Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2021; Parsons, 2021).

The current divergence in EEJ and Conservation viewpoints can be traced back to historical figures like John Muir. Muir- who is one of the pioneers of conservation - promoted preservationist viewpoints that regard wilderness as areas devoid of people (Martin, 2017). In contrast, a more equitable and just approach seeks to benefit people and nature mutually (Bennett, 2023). Market-driven elements have influenced biodiversity conservation with practices like park privatization, carbon trading, and biodiversity offsetting. Along with the promotion of green consumerism, offering potential conflict resolution, but also carrying the risk of coercion by local and state governments (Bennett, 2023; Martin, 2017; Jouffary, 2020). Coercion by local and state governments in biodiversity conservation can manifest through the imposition of market-driven practices on local communities, which can overwhelm them, leading to unequal power dynamics, loss of traditional resource rights, and environmental justice concerns (Bennett, 2023; Martin, 2017; Jouffary, 2020; Folchi, 2019; Gosalvez, 2020).

In a contemporary context, a more equitable and just approach seeks to harmonize benefits for both people and nature, recognizing the interconnectedness of human well-being and environmental health (Bennett, 2023; Martin, 2017). This evolution reflects a departure from historical preservationist viewpoints, like Muir's, toward a vision that aligns conservation practices with principles of justice and equity while acknowledging the utilitarian perspectives espoused by figures like Pinchot.

Due to dynamic conservation perspectives, historical displacement has undergone a notable transformation, shifting from forceful approaches¹⁵ to strategies that prioritize community engagement, particularly since the late 1980s (Folchi, 2019; Jouffary, 2020; OJS, OPC, 2023). This shift is attributed to a growing awareness of the social consequences associated with conservation efforts (Bennett, 2023). Within this evolving landscape, the emergence of

¹⁴ "Western Environmentalism occurs in affluent societies where they are able to focus on visible expressions, like membership in environmental groups. They do not have to put their lives on line in order to protect their environment. The support for conservation is strongest in more economically prosperous western democracies, and much weaker in the global south" (Martin, 2017).

¹⁵ Forceful Approaches refers to conservation methods that involve coercion, compulsion, or the exertion of direct authority to implement conservation measures. These approaches might have involved forcibly displacing communities, imposing regulations without community involvement, or using authoritarian methods to achieve conservation goals (Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2021).

'tragic choices' underscores the dilemma faced by decision-makers who must navigate the delicate balance between conservation imperatives and human rights, particularly in economically disadvantaged regions where underserved communities are disproportionately expected to bear the sacrifices for conservation goals (Martin, 2017).

As the discourse surrounding EEJ has gained prominence in the field of conservation, the historical neglect of EEJ within the field of ocean conservation and management has drawn substantial criticism. The neglect of EEJ includes the failure of ocean leaders to develop awareness and strategies around the systemic barriers that impede underserved communities' access to natural spaces and the meaningful participation of such communities in shaping ocean governance (Bennett, 2023; OJS, OPC, 2023). The resulting diversity in conservation perspectives has, unfortunately, fostered persistent disagreements and conflicts, preventing the attainment of a consensus on 'just conservation' within the field (Martin, 2017; Folchi, 2019).

Blue Justice

The traditional focus of EEJ on land-based issues has expanded to encompass the marine environment, referred to as 'Blue Justice.' This shift addresses the challenges posed by the growing ocean industries while promoting equitable access to coastal areas for underserved populations. Blue Justice builds upon EEJ principles and draws inspiration from related fields, such as participatory action research¹⁶ and community-based methods for addressing environmental and social challenges (Hall, 1984; Chambers, 1983; Bennet et al., 2023, Jouffray et al, 2020). This expansion of EEJ into the marine domain is in response to the rapid growth of various ocean industries, including offshore energy production, fishing, aquaculture, shipping, and tourism (Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Mascia, 2010; Garcia, 2018). This shift reflects a response to the practical implications arising from the escalating activities within these industries, encouraging stakeholders to consider EEJ principles (Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2021; Garcia, 2018; Jones, 2009). In these sectors, decisions often prioritize business development, which can overshadow the goal of providing equitable access to coastal areas for underrepresented populations (Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018).

Despite its academic recognition, the translation of Blue Justice into concrete policies has been limited (Bennett, 2021; Bennett, 2023) and methods for integrating EEJ principles into ocean conservation remains ambiguous (Bennett, 2021; Garcia, 2017; Jones, 2009). However, there has been an increase in the use of Blue Economy or Sustainable Ocean Economy¹⁷ in recent policy documents such as the Ocean Climate Action Plan (OCAP) and Ocean Justice Strategy

¹⁶ "Participatory Action Research (PAR) is an approach to research which has been used since the 1940s. It involves researchers and participants working together to understand a problematic situation and change it for the better. There are many definitions of the approach, which share some common elements." ([Institute of Development Studies, 2023](#)).

¹⁷ "The sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and job creation can support good-paying jobs, skills, training, and other economic benefits, ensure that healthy and plentiful seafood is widely available, and produce abundant and accessible ocean-based sources of energy, recreation, transportation, and trade" as informed by ([OJS, 2023](#); [NOAA, 2022](#))

(OSJ) released by the Ocean Policy Committee in March and December of 2023 (OCAP, OPC 2023; OJS, OPC 2023). The dynamic interpretation prompts a fundamental question: *Do we require a distinct term, or should we aim for a more inclusive understanding of EEJ that encompasses both land and sea?* Embracing the concept of Blue Justice offers advantages such as heightened awareness of coastal and marine issues, enhanced advocacy for affected communities, and the potential for customized policy solutions (Bennett, 2021; Bennett, 2023; Jones, 2009; Garcia, 2017; Avakian, 2021). Potential drawbacks include the risk of fragmenting the EEJ movement and diminishing its overall impact if not effectively integrated into existing EEJ frameworks (Bennett, 2021; Bennett, 2023; Jones, 2009; Garcia, 2017; Avakian, 2021).

In this literature review, we first delve into the definitions of the EEJ concept of “Blue Justice and then explore the historical evolution and foundational principles of equity and environmental justice (EEJ). This groundwork sets the stage for an examination of how EEJ applies to ocean management, considering theoretical frameworks and perspectives of Environmental Justice (EJ) and their implications for ocean equity. We discuss equitable access to nature, emphasizing the benefits and ecosystem services it provides, along with the concept of the “Nature Gap.” Our focus then shifts to disparities in ocean access and coastal resources and their impact on underserved communities. We extend our exploration of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), scrutinizing their definitions and types and evaluating the integration of EEJ principles into their design. We then explore strategies to promote equitable ocean access and MPA design, concluding with future challenges and practical recommendations. Throughout, we explore diverse perspectives, trace historical shifts, and observe the evolving landscape of EEJ.

Equity and Environmental Justice: Definitions, Core Principles, and Implementation

EEJ represents concepts and theories addressing who is recognized, included in decision-making processes, and who benefits from the distribution of environmental advantages and burdens (Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018; Mohai, 2009; Mohai, 1992; Gauna & Foster, 2003). Three prominent dimensions of EJ provide a foundational framework: recognitional justice, procedural justice, and distributive justice (Boillat et al., 2018; NOAA, 2023; Bullard, 2001; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002).

The concept of Distributive justice focuses on the equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens among communities (NOAA, 2023; Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2018; Agyeman & Bullard, 2001). In the broader context, distributive justice concerns the fair allocation of resources, goods, and opportunities within a society, considering factors such as wealth, income, and social status (Olsaretti, 2018; Honneth, 2004; Fraser, 1997). It centers on actual outcomes. For example, within the environmental realm, distributive justice can be seen in the allocation of resources for renewable energy initiatives (Bennett, 2018; Bennett, 2023). When designing policies and funding mechanisms to support renewable energy adoption, considerations must be made to ensure that underserved communities have equitable access to the benefits of clean energy. This ensures that the transition to sustainable energy sources not

only reduces environmental burdens but also addresses historical injustices by promoting equitable access to clean energy solutions.

Procedural justice highlights the inclusion of all voices in decision-making processes in environmental matters, focusing on elevating the inclusion of those who have traditionally not had a seat at the table (Boillat et al., 2018; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Bennett, 2018; Scott, 2013). This theory considers procedural justice to represent transparent, participatory, and equitable processes that allow all affected parties, including Indigenous groups and environmental organizations, to have a say in shaping international environmental policies, community-based conservation initiatives, eco-responsible business practices, conservation efforts, etc. (Parsons, 2021; De Santo, 2013; Stodolska, 2012; Jones, 2009; Bennett, 2023; Bennett et al., 2018; Martin, 2017; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Landau, 2020; Garcia, 2018). This concept addresses that a select few do not dominate decision-making and that the interests and knowledge of those directly impacted by changes in ocean policy are considered. Facilitating procedural justice involves identifying underserved stakeholders in the decision-making process and strategically broadening the participation of diverse voices to enhance inclusivity and fairness (Parsons, 2021; De Santo, 2013; Stodolska, 2012; Jones, 2009; Bennett, 2023; Bennett et al., 2018; Martin, 2017; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Landau, 2020; Garcia, 2018).

Recognitional justice, shaped by the theories of social philosophers Axel Honneth and Nancy Fraser, represents a shift in 21st-century justice theories and identity politics¹⁸ (Fraser, 1997; Agyeman & Bullard, 2001). Recognitional justice is a dimension of social justice that places a strong emphasis on recognizing intrinsic human dignity and acknowledging the distinctions between subaltern groups and the dominant society (Honneth, 2004; Fraser, 1997). While distributive justice deals with the redistribution of tangible resources, recognition is a phenomenological¹⁹ experience intrinsic to individuals and groups (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Scott, 2013; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Garcia, 2013; Honneth, 2004; Fraser, 1997). Recognitional justice is often subject to varying interpretations, primarily with respect to the cultural and historical significance of specific natural resources or places to particular communities (Bullard, 2001; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Landau et al., 2020; Martin et al., 2017; Bennett, 2018). From the perspective of cultural significance, recognitional justice identifies how policies and decisions concerning these resources or places consider the profound cultural and historical values they hold for those communities (Bullard, 2021; Bennett, 2021; Gauna & Foster, 2003).

Participation

The participation of communities in environmental management and conservation forms an important foundation for the equitable implementation of EEJ principles and is outlined by the

¹⁸ Identity politics is politics based on a particular identity, such as race, nationality, religion, gender, sexual orientation, social background, social class. (Fraser, 1997)

¹⁹ Phenomenological refers to an approach or perspective that focuses on the subjective and lived experiences of individuals, emphasizing their perceptions, feelings, and interpretations of phenomena. (NLM, 2019)

classical framework known as Arnstein’s Ladder of Participation (Arnstein, 1969; Bennett, 2018). At the lower rungs of participation, communities often find themselves relegated to passive roles and lack meaningful involvement in decision-making (Arnstein, 1969). For example, residents in urban and coastal planning and development may be only informed about major projects affecting their neighborhoods through public meetings. However, these interactions can become a form of non-participation where residents voice concerns but wield little influence over final decisions. This limited participation effectively sidelines them from achieving the goals of EEJ, which require active and meaningful involvement in environmental decision-making (Bullard, 2001). At higher levels of participation, citizens become active partners and decision-makers (Arnstein, 1969; Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2021). Meaningful citizen engagement through delegation and partnership becomes a powerful tool for addressing disparities and achieving equitable environmental outcomes (Scott, 2013; Arnstein, 1969; Blackburn, 2023).

Arnstein's Ladder (1969)
Degrees of Citizen Participation

Figure 1. Arnstein’s Ladder of Participation²⁰.

The pursuit of EEJ necessitates a shift from passive forms of participation toward more active and influential roles for citizens, where their voices are not only heard but also respected, valued, and acted upon in shaping environmental policies and practices (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Scott, 2013; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Garcia, 2013).

²⁰ Description: Arnstein's Ladder of Participation is a seminal framework that illustrates the varying degrees of citizen involvement in decision-making processes, ranging from non-participation to citizen control. This framework plays a central role in understanding and addressing issues related to citizen engagement in EEJ. It categorizes different levels of participation, offering insight into how communities can progress from passive information recipients to active partners and decision-makers in shaping environmental policies and achieving equitable outcomes. (Arnstein, 1969).

Why does access to nature, oceans, and MPAs matter at all?

Nature benefits and ecosystem services

The significance of access to nature, including coastal areas and oceans, stems from the broad suite of benefits that nature provides for individual and community well-being. The concept of ecosystem services provides one framework for understanding the value of nature in providing tangible benefits to human societies (Bennet, 2021; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Parsons, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2023). Ecosystem services encompass a wide array of contributions ecosystems make to human life. These include provisioning services, such as clean air and water that ensure a supply of fresh and clean resources, and pollination that supports agriculture (Bennet, 2021; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Parsons, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2023). Regulating services, such as flood regulation through wetlands and storm protection by coastal ecosystems, help control natural processes and maintain environmental conditions (Bennet, 2021; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2023). Ecosystems also provide cultural services by offering recreational opportunities, like hiking and bird-watching, as well as aesthetic and spiritual experiences that connect individuals to the beauty and tranquility of nature (Bennet, 2021; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; South, 2020; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2023).

Research on nature's benefits highlights substantive health benefits from nature, which can be considered both cultural and provisioning services (South, 2020; Dawson, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Bennett, 2021; Visbeck, 2018). For example, spending time in natural environments is associated with improved physical and mental health, reduced stress, lower blood pressure, enhanced cognitive function, and an overall better quality of life (South, 2020; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2022). Researchers estimate that each dollar invested in creating and maintaining park trails can lead to savings of nearly three dollars in healthcare costs—an advantage that remains unavailable to the most economically distressed communities (South 2018; Jaffe 2015; Rowland-Shea 2020). Thus, ensuring access to nature becomes critical for promoting public health and well-being, ultimately leading to reduced healthcare costs. In contrast, individuals and communities experience negative impacts or adverse health outcomes due to their limited access to nature, which can be termed a 'health burden' (Landau et al, 2020). Compared to the national average, regions with predominantly white populations experience a health burden that is 11.7% lower, while regions with predominantly non-white populations face a 7.8% higher health burden (Landau et al., 2020). The socioeconomic aspects of this issue emphasize that wealth and economic well-being significantly impact individuals' life chances (Fishkin, 1983; Weber, 1978). These findings illuminate the limited access to nature often experienced by underrepresented communities, resulting in adverse consequences.

What is a Nature gap?

There are well-documented racial and economic disparities in nature access in the United States, depriving these communities of nature's benefits ([Landau et al., 2020](#); [Rowland-Shea et al., 2020](#); [Ocean Protection Council, 2022](#); [Reineman et al., 2016](#); [Garcia, 2017](#); [Floyd, 1999](#)). The concept of the 'Nature Gap,' which highlights such disparities in nature access ([Rowland-Shea, 2020](#); [Jones, 2009](#); [Landau et al. in 2020](#); [Bullard, 2001](#); [Agyeman & Bullard, 2001](#); [Boillat et al, 2018](#); [Reineman et al., 2016](#); [Christensen et al, 2017](#); [Scott et al., 2013](#); [Garcia, 2017](#); [Stodolska et al., 2012](#); [Bennett et al, 2023](#)). For example, communities of color are three times more likely to reside in nature-deprived areas compared to white communities, with 74 percent of such communities in the contiguous United States experiencing limited access ([Rowland-Shea, 2020](#)). Similarly, this discrepancy is pronounced in low-income communities, where 70 percent of low-income communities grapple with nature-deprived areas, representing a 20 percent higher absence of nature access compared to economically advantaged communities ([Rowland-Shea, 2020](#); [Martin et al, 2017](#); [Christensen et al, 2017](#)). The widespread separation from nature near underserved communities exemplifies distributive justice, the concept of understanding the fair distribution of resources and benefits within society ([Bennett, 2021](#); [Garcia, 2017](#)). Underserved populations also frequently bear the brunt of declining ecosystem services due to climate change, experiencing reduced recreational opportunities, limited food resources, and diminished access to fisheries for their livelihoods ([Bennett et al, 2023](#)). of nature's benefits ([Landau et al., 2020](#); [Rowland-Shea et al., 2020](#); [Ocean Protection Council, 2022](#); [Reineman et al., 2016](#); [Garcia, 2017](#); [Floyd, 1999](#)).

Income inequality contributes significantly to limited access to recreational resources. In southern California, in areas where children have less access to outdoor spaces for physical activity, there tends to be a higher prevalence of overweight and obese children ([Garcia, 2017](#)). The issue of nature gaps illuminates the complex factors contributing to reduced access within underrepresented communities, often emphasizing the need for a science-based understanding of the elements that influence minority engagement with nature ([Floyd, 1999](#); [Ocean Protection Council, 2022](#); [NOAA, 2023](#); [Executive Order 14096](#); [Bennett et al., 2018](#)). Common obstacles hindering participation include safety concerns, financial constraints, and site accessibility issues ([Stodolska et al., 2012](#); [Crellin, 2022](#); [Scott et al., 2013](#); [Garcia, 2017](#)).

Safety concerns and fears of people of color for spending time in natural areas are grounded in a history of exclusion of businesses and violence against individuals. For example, in Manhattan Beach, CA, in the 1920s, a black-owned seaside resort was dismantled by racist city council members, and the family was forced to flee the city ([CEO, 2022](#)). Black individuals who were recreating in natural areas have been threatened or attacked by racist white individuals. Examples include Christian Cooper, a Black birder in Central Park who had the police called on him by a white woman when he asked her to follow park rules, and Ahmaud Arbery, a Black runner, who was murdered by three white men while on a run outside ([Chaudhury, 2020](#); [Yankah, 2021](#)).

There has been historical underrepresentation of racial and ethnic minorities in national parks due to the diverse factors that impact outdoor recreation participation within minority communities (Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Gosalvez, 2020; Dawsons, 2018; Gurney, 2021; Jones, 2009). Poorer Americans are significantly less likely to utilize publicly funded park and recreation resources. Affluent individuals are three times more inclined to visit national parks, and similar patterns are observed for state, regional, and local parks (Scott, 2013; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Floyd, 1999). Preferences and motivations for engaging with nature can vary significantly among different cultural and racial groups, with an emphasis on factors such as convenience, community engagement, and the availability of amenities (Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017). Hispanic and African American visitors to national parks tend to prioritize developed facilities, larger group sizes, and the social benefits of outdoor activities compared to their white counterparts (Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Christensen, 2017). Tailoring outdoor recreation and park access initiatives to the diverse needs and interests of minority communities promotes greater inclusivity and enhances the overall enjoyment and utilization of natural spaces by a wider range of the population (U.S. Department of the Interior 1997:55; Floyd, 1999; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Scott, 2013; Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017).

In the case of beaches in California, identifying these distinctions is the key. The concentration of poverty and affluence has led to a two-tier system of publicly funded park and recreation provision in the U.S., where wealthier communities enjoy better-funded and higher-quality amenities, while inner cities and poorer communities lack basic funding and historical access to such resources (Scott, 2013; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Floyd, 1999). Recognizing and addressing these economic disparities is essential to achieving a more equitable and inclusive outdoor recreation landscape.

EJ has often overlooked the unique challenges faced by disabled people in their interactions with nature. Other fields, such as disability studies and accessibility advocacy, have focused on addressing gaps in access that are specific to individuals with disabilities (Lau, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2021). This entails addressing a spectrum of needs, including providing sign language interpreters for deaf individuals during guided nature tours, improving accessibility in national parks to accommodate wheelchair users on uneven terrain, and making information accessible through braille materials for blind individuals, among other accommodations (Lau, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2021; Floyd, 1999; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Scott, 2013; Gosalvez, 2020). To attain a comprehensive and impartial approach to environmental justice, it is essential to incorporate the perspectives and requirements of the disabled community (Lau, 2021; Martin, 2017; Bennett, 2021).

Discussion of key theoretical frameworks and perspectives related to EJ.

Our investigation of key theoretical frameworks and perspectives related to EEJ involves analyzing the language employed in federal and state executive orders, including federal and state of California agencies dealing with natural resources. We apply the practical applications of

the EEJ principles in governance and policymaking, acknowledging the notable shifts in policy and definitions over time. To provide context, we present three appendices:

- Appendix 1: The Federal and State of California Executive Orders
- Appendix 2: Federal agencies tasked with overseeing various aspects of environmental protection, including pollution, oceans, and natural resources.
- Appendix 3: California's natural resources agencies.

Federal and State of California Executive Orders

Each Executive Order maintains a distinct focus and scope, with some concentrating on climate-related impacts and others addressing the disproportionate effects on minority and low-income populations while emphasizing meaningful involvement in decision-making processes. They all recognize the importance of addressing the cumulative impacts of environmental hazards, the legacy of racism, and systemic barriers that have contributed to existing disparities. The initial Executive Order (EO) 12898, enacted in 1992, set a narrow precedent for EEJ due to vague directives and limited enforcement mechanisms. The EO urged federal agencies to incorporate EJ into their missions, identify adverse effects on minority and low-income populations, and to establish an Interagency Working Group on EJ (EO 12898, 1992). The order lacked specific directives for agencies, leading to lenient and varied approaches along with inconsistent enforcement and accountability; the focus on procedural aspects, such as the Interagency working group, overshadowed tangible actions. There is a noticeable gap of 21 years, from 2000 to 2021, during which there was no federal EO specifically targeting environmental justice.

The recent resurgence of EEJ policies, beginning with EO 13985 in 2021, marks a renewed emphasis on the issue of EJ (Appendix 1). EO 14008 set a broader precedent for EEJ by establishing the Justice40 initiative, aiming to channel 40 percent of federal investments' benefits to underserved communities (OJS, OPC 2023; EO 14008, 2021). The following EOs' were able to build off EO 14008, paving the way for executive branch agencies to integrate EJ into their missions through EO 14091, which charges the federal government with advancing equity for all, addressing persistent poverty and inequality (OJS, OPC 2023; EO 14091, 2023). The later orders highlight climate justice; climate injustice is that those who have contributed the least to climate change are often the ones who suffer the most from its consequences (Schlosberg and Collins, 2014; Bennett, 2021; Avakian, 2021). In EO 14096 enacted in 2023, the latest definition also recognizes the legacy of racism and systemic barriers in alignment with evolving understandings of EJ over time. Climate justice, an extension of environmental justice, seeks to address the unequal distribution of climate change impacts, particularly focusing on marginalized communities (Schlosberg and Collins, 2014; Bennett, 2021). Climate justice closely aligns with this evolving definition, emphasizing equitable treatment and just involvement, particularly for marginalized communities, as required by EO 14096 (Appendix 1).

EJ definitions have evolved since then spanning publication years from 1994 to 2023, reflecting the evolving understanding of environmental and climate justice. In contrast, Federal

and State Executive Orders from 2021 significantly shift the EJ focus by introducing a broader interpretation of EJ (Appendix 1). For example, recent EJ EOs incorporate climate-related impacts and climate change considerations, thus elevating the principles of climate justice (Schlosberg and Collins, 2014; Bennett, 2021; Martin, 2017; Mascia, 2010). California's EO N-16-22 stands out as a notable development in EJ for its innovative approach to introducing state-level involvement. The EO concentrates on embedding equity considerations within the state's agencies and departments, marking a stride toward the integration of EJ principles into the state's governance (EO N-16-22, 2022).

In conclusion, the analysis of Appendix 1 reveals a dynamic landscape in the evolution of EJ definitions. The observed patterns, from the narrow focus of early orders to the broader interpretations introduced in recent years, reflect the responsiveness of governance to changing societal and environmental priorities. The emphasis on climate justice in newer EO signals a recognition of the urgent need to address climate-related impacts on vulnerable communities. There appears to be a noticeable gap in relating EJ principles to ocean-related matters and ensuring equitable access to natural resources until later EO's drafted in 2023.

Federal Agencies Tasked with Overseeing Various Aspects of Environmental Protection, Including Pollution, Oceans, and Natural Resources

The federal agencies dealing with pollution, oceans, and natural resources have committed to EJ in a manner that only informs inclusivity, equitable protection, and meaningful community involvement (Appendix 2). Regardless of their distinct missions, these agencies have provided uniform definitions that emphasize the fair and meaningful engagement of all individuals, irrespective of race, color, national origin, gender, sexual orientation, tribal affiliation, religion, disability, or income, in shaping environmental laws, regulations, and policies. Common objectives across agencies' EJ definitions include equitable safeguarding against environmental and health hazards and ensuring access for all communities to a sustainable and healthy environment which aligns with the broader framework of distributive and procedural justice.

EPA is an agency that was established in 1970 by President Nixon. The definition for environmental justice did not originate until 1992 and is now uniformly being used across agencies and governments ([EPA, 2023](#)). However, the definitions vary in scope, in part reflecting the distinct missions and priorities of each agency (Appendix 2). The Department of Commerce (DOC) adopts EJ principles by highlighting their role in economic growth, environmental data stewardship, and property protection. The DOC's focus aligns with distributive justice by striving for the equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens across communities. The branch agencies' definitions have also evolved, mirroring the changing priorities within these federal agencies. While they all share common themes, these variations underscore the agencies' diverse roles and responsibilities in addressing EEJ issues within their domains.

For example, agencies under DOC and within NOAA (e.g. CINMS, ONMS, NMFS, OPC) encompass all three dimensions of EJ by emphasizing equitable protection, access, and

opportunity for underserved communities during the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws. While the Ocean Policy Committee is not directly under NOAA, they share the idea of just treatment and meaningful involvement of all people in federal agency decision-making related to the ocean - an element of recognitional justice.

On the other hand, agencies under the Department of Interior (DOI) (e.g. BLM, NPS, BOEM, USFWS) prioritize ecological, economic, cultural, and social impacts for outstanding management of natural and cultural resources with a sustainable, inclusive, and accessible approach. USDA stands out with its procedural and distributive justice approach focusing only on governmental programs by emphasizing the opportunity for all populations to comment, share benefits, and avoid disproportionate impacts from government programs affecting health or the environment. While USFS is not directly under DOI, they share the same message of emphasizing equal access to the decision-making process for a healthy environment. The approach of DOI indicates a multi-dimensional approach that incorporates aspects of both recognitional and distributive justice.

California's Natural Resources Agencies

The EJ definitions among California natural resource agencies show both commonalities and differences, demonstrating a shared commitment to fairness and inclusivity with room for organizational priorities. Established in 2018, the California Natural Resources Agency, California Department of Conservation, and California Department of Water Resources base their definitions on common legal foundations of recognitional justice, emphasizing fair treatment across different demographics in environmental law matters. This legal basis suggests a unified approach to framing EJ principles. California agencies (Appendix 3), including the California Environmental Protection Agency, reinforce the EJ commitment. Their definitions stress fairness regardless of race, color, national origin, or income, highlighting community involvement in shaping laws for natural surroundings. These definitions collectively highlight diverse approaches and priorities in the pursuit of equitable environmental protection and access.

Despite this unity, differences emerge in the emphasis and scope of agency definitions. The California State Lands Commission stresses that traditionally disadvantaged groups should not be excluded. California State Parks adds rare core values of cultural diversity and accessibility, emphasizing everyone's right, including persons with disabilities, to access recreational opportunities. Each agency introduces nuanced language, specifying fair treatment scope and prevention of disproportionate environmental consequences. While most agencies established their definitions in 2018, the California Fish and Wildlife Commission (2021), California Ocean Protection Council (2022), and California Environmental Protection Agency (2023) showcase timeline diversity, indicating evolving priorities.

Additional Considerations

Additionally, the rarity of equity plans in both federal agencies like the California Ocean Protection Council and NOAA Fisheries (Appendix 2; Appendix 3) and state agencies signifies a

noteworthy commitment to a comprehensive approach in addressing environmental justice concerns.

The publication years of state EJ definitions span from 1992 to 2023, reflecting the evolving understanding of EJ. References to specific executive orders underscore the legal frameworks guiding these federal and state agencies. However, an expectation of the USFS's definition established in 1997 sets it apart (Appendix 3). Notably, there was a gap in the state of California's agencies' EJ definitions from 1992 to 2018, spanning 26 years. These insights provide a practical view of agencies' interpretations of environmental justice, showcasing a dynamic landscape shaped by both shared principles and distinctive organizational values.

Disparities in Ocean Access and Coastal Resources/ Application of Equity to Oceans

The oceans, covering over 70% of the Earth's surface, hold a wealth of resources that sustain livelihoods, ecosystems, and countless species. However, persistent disparities in access and benefits are evident across coastal regions. Underserved communities face pronounced challenges in accessing beaches, fishing grounds, and other marine and coastal amenities, leading to disparities documented by various researchers (Martin, 2017; Christensen & King, 2017; Mascia, 2010; Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021; Giakoumi, 2018; Reineman, 2016; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Garcia, 2018; Crellin, 2022; Floyd, 1999). These disparities are often shaped by socioeconomic, racial, and geographic factors (Clinton, 1994; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Pellow, 2018; Landau, 2020; Reineman, 2016; Bennett, 2023; Giakoumi, 2018; Mascia, 2010; Mohai, 2009; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Jouffray, 2020; Newson, 2022; Parsons, 2021). Socioeconomic factors, notably income disparities, and issues of equity and race, frequently influence participation in ocean-related activities and the receipt of associated benefits (Scott, 2013; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Bennett, 2023; Boillat, 2018; Blount, 2007; Lau et al, 2021; Clinton, 1994; Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Landau et al, 2020; Reineman, 2016; Martin, 2017; Christensen & King, 2017; Mascia, 2010; Stodolska, 2012; Garcia, 2017; Mohai, 2009; Newson, 2022; Gauna & Foster, 2003). The establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in the Florida Keys had minimal economic impact but significantly affected various user groups, leading to heightened social-psychological impacts (Mascia, 2010; Dobryznski and Nicholson, 2001). This situation resulted in escalated conflicts and concerns among user groups, including commercial and subsistence fishers, the tourism industry, and recreational divers and snorkelers regarding access to the MPA (Mascia, 2010; Dobryznski and Nicholson, 2001). The primary issue revolves around perceived inequity, with snorkelers and divers enjoying privileged access over commercial and subsistence fishers (Mascia, 2010; Dobryznski and Nicholson, 2001).

In the case of the Gulf of Mexico, a survey conducted from Texas to Key West examined the perspectives of fishermen on the potential of the establishment of MPA (Masica, 2010; Thomas, 1999). The primary concern identified was the economic impact resulting from displacement from their traditional fishing areas (Mascia, 2010; Thomas, 1999). In the Florida

Keys case, fishermen expressed secondary concern related to the vital importance of social equity for resource access and fair enforcement in MPA management (Mascia, 2010; Thomas, 1999; Blount, 2007). The apprehension about enforcement centered around the potential lapses that could lead to economic and access inequities within the MPAs (Mascia, 2010; Thomas, 1999; Blount, 2007; Garcia, 2017; Jones, 2009). The cases serve as compelling examples of how unequal resource allocation, economic disparities, and issues of equity and race can impact communities and user groups differently, resulting in both economic and social consequences.

As for racial and geographic factors, the demographic compositions of different coastal areas highlight the complexity of disparities in ocean access. Various beaches and marine sites may attract diverse or homogeneous crowds based on factors such as residential patterns, availability of amenities, perceived inclusiveness, community proximity, and historical visitation patterns (Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Garcia, 2017; Garcia, 2018; Stodolska, 2012). These dynamics are intricately linked to a historical legacy of discrimination (Crellin, 2022; Mohai, 2009; Mohai, 1992, Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Garcia, 2017; Garcia, 2018; Stodolska, 2012). Similarly, discriminatory policies such as EO 9066 of 1942 by President Roosevelt called for Japanese Americans' forced relocation and internment during World War II. Effectively disrupting Japanese American communities and impacting their access to coastal areas and its resources which was prominent in California, later shaping its dynamics (Spickard, 2009; NPS, 2000). In a similar context, in the 1930s, repatriation disproportionately affected Mexicans and Mexican Americans, with half million a million individuals becoming targets of one of the largest mass removal operations sanctioned by the US government, leading to the destruction of entire neighborhoods and communities in California and all over the United States (Guerin-Gonzales, 1996). This period of immigration and repatriation left a lasting impact, instilling a constant fear of expulsion and disrupting the lives and dreams of Mexican immigrants and Mexican Americans, shaping their experiences in coastal regions like California and beyond (Guerin-Gonzales, 1996).

In light of these historical injustices, the consequences continue to shape current challenges in accessing the California Coast. The constrained access to recreational resources along the California Coast poses a growing concern due to its function as a common pool of natural resources, along with increasing limitations due to climate change and the growing population (Reineman, 2016; Christensen, 2017; Martin, 2017; Garcia, 2018). The issue of access to the California coast raised concern among 62 percent of California resident voters. Public transportation accessibility was considered a barrier by 68 percent of respondents (Rowland- Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012). Notably, in California Central Valley, African-American residents are found to visit the coast less frequently, with 39 percent and 33 percent, respectively, visiting less than once a year (Rowland- Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012).

Income also impacts coastal visits, as those earning over \$60,000 annually are more likely to visit, while the cost of visiting the coast particularly affects individuals aged 30 to 39

and families with children (Scott, 2013; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012). Additionally, 75 percent cited a shortage of reasonably priced overnight accommodations as a significant issue, with Latino voters and families with children expressing even greater concern (Rowland-Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012). Additionally, the lack of affordable overnight accommodations is a greater concern for the respondents aged 18 to 39 and families with children, while limited affordable parking options troubled 78 percent (Reineham, 2016; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020). (Rowland- Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017). The information is based on a statewide survey of California voters conducted in October 2016 by UCLA's Institute of the Environment and Sustainability and the Field Poll and from a database assembled by the California Coastal Commission (Christensen, 2017; Reineman, 2016).

Understanding the nuanced preferences and challenges of diverse beachgoers, as revealed through the statewide poll and beach surveys (Christensen, 2017), sheds light on a spectrum of needs expressed by different demographics (Christensen, 2017; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012). Young beachgoers visit solo, rely on public transportation, and worry about expenses (Christensen & King, 2017). Families prioritize child-friendly areas and accommodations, while Latino and African-American beachgoers seek amenities but share concerns about costs and safety (Scott, 2013; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017; Landau et al, 2020; Garcia, 2017; Stodolska, 2012). Older beachgoers value parking and have similar cost concerns. Visitors traveling longer distances visit less often and mainly worry about expenses (Rowland-Shea, 2020; Christensen & King, 2017). Exploring the needs and preferences of additional demographics, such as Indigenous and Asian communities, would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse beachgoing population in California.

However, the insights into the diverse needs and challenges faced by different beachgoers underscore the pervasive problem of racism on beaches (Crellin, 2022; Bennett, 2023; Mohai, 2009; Mohai, 1992, Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013; Garcia, 2017; Garcia, 2018; Stodolska, 2012). For instance, the culture surrounding surfing, often portrayed as a transformative and connective space, has historically excluded non-white participants (Crellin, 2022). This exclusion perpetuates the dominance of white individuals in the surfing community, limiting opportunities for surfers of color. Which aligns surfing with beliefs rooted in white neoliberal ideals of individualism, self-reliance, risk-taking, and progress (Crellin, 2022). For example, the exclusionary aspect of the surfing world was exemplified when Andrew Sherlock Mills, an African American surfer in Jupiter, Florida, had his board stolen and nailed to a tree by a group of white surfers. This racist act was reminiscent of a lynching, as detailed by the Instagram account Black.surfers (Crellin, 2022; Pierson, 2023). Surfing has a troubling legacy of some individuals like the famous surfer Mickey Dora known as "the King of Malibu", who promoted white supremacy and divisive beliefs within the surfing community. Such examples serve as stark reminders that racial discrimination has seeped into various aspects of beach and coastal

culture (Crellin, 2022). Further highlighting the importance of conducting a thorough examination and fostering inclusivity and equity for all beach goers and surfers, regardless of their racial background.

Impacts of Ocean Access Disparities on Communities

Amidst the challenges posed by racial discrimination in coastal communities, equitable access to coastal spaces is pivotal. An array of consequences from limited ocean access affect mental and physical health, recreational opportunities, cultural practices, and socioeconomic livelihoods. Equitable access to coastal spaces is pivotal for fostering community cohesion, preserving cultural heritage, and facilitating healthy recreational activities (Martin, 2017; Christensen & King, 2017; Mascia, 2010; Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021; Giakoumi, 2018; Reineman, 2016; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Garcia, 2018; Crellin, 2022; Floyd, 1999). The issue lies in the need for policies to recognize and consider the profound intrinsic value and cultural significance these areas hold for particular groups (Martin, 2017; Christensen & King, 2017; Mascia, 2010; Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021; Giakoumi, 2018; Reineman, 2016; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Garcia, 2018)

The economic significance of beach recreation, which contributes billions annually to a state's economy, underscores the critical need for equitable access for marginalized communities. For example, A 2005 estimate indicates a contribution of beach recreation at around \$2.25-\$7.5 billion annually in California (Pendleton & Kildow, 2006; Rehinman, 2016). For instance, surveys of beachgoers found that the average value of a day trip to the beach based on economic demand is \$36.74, and the average cost of traveling to the beach and returning home—excluding expenses such as parking, food, and activities—was \$22.09 (Christensen & King, 2017). This cost and time of travel to the beach limits beach access, especially for those who live more than a 10-mile radius or an hour away- a reflection of unequal distributive justice (Rehinman, 2016). This cost - estimated in 2017 - has assuredly risen due to inflation. The economic lens emphasizes the concept of distributive justice, urging California to pursue an equitable distribution of economic contributions, considering factors such as wealth, income, and social status (Rehinman, 2016; Christensen, 2017). The challenge of limited coastal space, coupled with the impact of rising sea levels and climate change, demands that access to coastal resources remains equitable as coastal landscapes change and population increases (Christensen & King, 2017; Rehinman, 2016; Martin, 2017; Mascia, 2017; Garcia, 2018; Bennett, 2023, Bennett, 2021).

Conflicts over conservation often pit relatively affluent groups against economically disadvantaged ones (Martin, 2017), highlighting the complexity of achieving conservation goals while ensuring equitable access to coastal resources - a case of both distributive justice and procedural justice. Consider the disparities faced by user groups in the Key West MPA, where conflicts over conservation have arisen, pitting economically disadvantaged user groups, such as subsistence fishers, against more affluent stakeholders, like recreational divers, snorkelers, and the tourism industries (Mascia, 2010; Dobryznski and Nicholson, 2001). For example, economic

and social environments (e.g., urban neighborhoods in Los Angeles county²¹ with often marginalized communities like those in historically discriminated against Mexican American areas far away from coastal areas) are often related to poverty and disadvantaged social status. The case reveals the coupled issue of the lack of distributive justice and procedural justice. Such conditions significantly constrain the recreation behavior of ethnic and racial minorities (Floyd, 1998; Floyd, Bocarro, & Thomson, 2008; Sanders-Phillips, 2000; Stodolska, 2012; Shinew, Acevedo, & Izenstark, 2011). In the US, disparities in access to nature are evident, with African-American, Latino, Asian, Native American, and low-income families more likely than white families to inhabit regions lacking the benefits of natural spaces, such as nearby safe outdoor areas, clean water, unpolluted air, and diverse wildlife (Rowland-Shea, 2020). The distributive justice issue extends to housing disparities, as coastal areas are often associated with unaffordable housing, exacerbating challenges for marginalized communities in securing not only natural spaces but also the broader benefits of coastal living (Martin, 2017; Christensen & King, 2017; Mascia, 2010; Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021; Giakoumi, 2018; Reineman, 2016; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Garcia, 2018; Crellin, 2022; Floyd, 1999). This underlines the interconnectedness of economic well-being and equitable access to coastal resources.

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)/ National Marine Sanctuary: Definitions and Types

Understanding the conservation efforts and the role of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) is essential for examining their impact on marine ecosystems and the broader social environment. In California, MPAs showcase a diverse array of classifications, illustrating the adaptability of this conservation strategy to the state's coastal and marine environments, including State Marine Reserves (SMRs), State Marine Parks (SMPs), State Marine Conservation Areas for Educational and Research Purposes (SMCAs-ER), and State Marine Recreational Management Areas (SMRMAs). These MPAs include National Marine Sanctuaries (NMS), managed by NOAA, which are designed to safeguard significant marine environments, from pristine coral reefs to historical shipwrecks, often imposing restrictions on activities like fishing and prohibiting oil exploration to protect their ecological and historical value (NOAA, 2023; CINMS, 2023). In addition, California features a variety of state MPAs, such as State Marine Reserves (SMRs) that strictly prohibit extractive activities, State Marine Parks (SMPs) designed to balance conservation with recreational activities, and State Marine Conservation Areas (SMCAs) aimed at protecting and conserving marine habitats and ecosystems while allowing certain recreational and commercial fishing activities (CDFW, 2023; CINMS, 2023; NOAA, 2023). The state also incorporates State Marine Conservation Areas for Educational and Research Purposes (SMCAs-ER) that support scientific research and environmental education, along with State Marine Recreational Management Areas (SMRMAs) striving to harmonize conservation with

²¹ "In 2021, Los Angeles County had the state's highest poverty rate, with more than a quarter of residents living in poverty (using the California Poverty Measure). That amounts to more than 2.5 million people. The county's "deep poverty rate," encompassing the poorest of the poor, is also the state's second highest, at 6.7 percent. Other high-poverty regions include Orange County and the Central Coast." ([CATO, 2021](#)).

recreational fishing by promoting sustainable fishing practices (NOAA, 2023; Bennett, 2021; Mascia, 2010; Garcia, 2018; CDFW, 2023).

Ecologically, these MPAs offer numerous advantages, including habitat restoration, support for overexploited fish stocks, and the protection of imperiled species (NOAA, 2023; Bennett, 2021; Garcia, 2018). On the socioeconomic front, they promote sustainable fisheries management, stimulate local economies through tourism, and provide vital educational resources for environmental awareness and conservation ethics (Jones, 2009; NOAA, 2023; Christensen & King, 2017; OPC, 2022). In summary, California's comprehensive system of MPAs, spanning both National Marine Sanctuaries and various state MPA types, plays a pivotal role in preserving marine ecosystems, ensuring the welfare of marine life, and strengthening coastal communities.

Equity & Environmental Justice in Context of Marine Protected Areas

An examination of the intersection between EEJ and MPAs reveals fundamental questions about the fair distribution of benefits within the realm of marine conservation. While MPAs in the US, Canada, and many other countries primarily aim to preserve biodiversity and enhance ecosystem health, their establishment and management can unintentionally perpetuate environmental injustices (Jones, 2009; De Santo, 2013; Masica, 2010; Garcia, 2017). For example, Indigenous and underserved communities have often been excluded or faced marginalization during MPA decision-making processes, pointing to issues of recognitional and procedural justice (Bennett, 2023; De Santo, 2013; Garcia, 2018; Parsons, 2021). This marginalization can be attributed to a combination of historical, social, and economic factors (Jones, 2009). Historical injustices, such as land dispossession and colonization, place Indigenous communities at a socio-economic disadvantage which further limits their effective participation in MPA decision-making - a reflection of distributive justice concerns (Jones, 2009; Parsons, 2021). Systemic racism within decision-making structures further perpetuates the marginalization of these communities, as discriminatory practices limit their involvement and influence in MPA designations (Bennett, 2023). Inadequate representation within decision-making bodies often results in the neglect of their interests and needs, including gender-specific concerns, which highlight the challenges in achieving procedural justice (De Santo, 2013).

Economic interests, often favored by dominant groups - particularly white men - can take precedence during MPA decision-making, exacerbating gendered impacts and diminishing the rights and interests of Indigenous and underrepresented communities, which opposes procedural justice (Mascia, 2010; Parsons, 2021; Jones, 2009; Gurney, 2021). Power imbalances also play a significant role, with dominant groups typically exerting more influence and neglecting the concerns and needs of women and gender-diverse individuals in these communities (Parsons, 2021; Mascia, 2010; Jones, 2009; Gurney, 2021).

The implications of MPA establishment and management on EJ are far-reaching, necessitating a focus on inclusion and representation to address gendered impacts and the lack of procedural justice (Parsons, 2021). In California's dynamic coastal environment, stakeholders,

including Indigenous groups, local communities, government agencies, and environmental organizations, play various roles in MPA designation. Noting that the level of inclusion and participation varies among these groups (Arnstein, 1969; Bennett, 2021). Indigenous communities are gradually becoming integrated into the MPA processes, often in the form of co-management, reflecting elements of tokenism (Arnstein, 1969; Bennett, 2021; Parsons, 2021). Local communities do have opportunities for participation but often face limitations in their involvement, thus reflecting the non-participation rung of Arnstein's ladder, which can only go so far (Arnstein, 1969). Government agencies and environmental organizations also contribute to the MPA designation process by collectively creating a complex landscape of interactions and potential improvements in the relationship between MPAs and EJ (Masica, 2010; Bennett, 2021). It is vital to recognize the gendered impacts of spatial enclosures on resource access and acknowledge that even in cases where ecosystem services programs aim to address unequal distribution, local communities and Indigenous people rarely benefit from such projects- again reflecting tokenism, procedural and distributive justice (Arnstein, 1969; Parsons, 2021; Bennett, 2021; Gauna & Foster, 2003).

Historical Context and Emergence of EEJ as a Field of Study

The concept of EEJ in the US originated from the concerns of African-American communities who protested against the inequitable distribution of environmental hazards, notably toxic waste sites (Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003). Its roots can be traced to the 1978 Love Canal pollution scandal in Niagara Falls, New York. The Love Canal incident involved a neighborhood built on top of a former chemical dump site (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). Residents, many of whom were low-income and predominantly African-American, began to experience severe health issues due to toxic chemical exposure from the buried waste (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). This crisis exposed the unjust pollution burden marginalized communities bore, igniting the EJ movement (Agyeman & Bullard, 2002; Dawson, 2021). While pollution and climate change became focal points for predominantly white and affluent conservation groups in the 1970s, communities of color had long been grappling with issues like access to clean air, water, and basic services such as waste disposal (Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005; Ludwig, 2023). This extended history of environmental injustice spans over five centuries. It is characterized by practices like locating polluting industries near Black and impoverished communities, resulting in inhaling harmful nitrogen dioxide and blood contamination with dioxin (Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005; Ludwig, 2023).

During this period in the EEJ movement, the movement was closely intertwined with the broader context of the civil rights movement. Consequently, the early EEJ movement significantly influenced the trajectory of environmental and social justice in the United States (Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005; Ludwig, 2023). The civil rights movement, known for its tireless

advocacy for racial equality and justice, intersected with the burgeoning EEJ movement in various ways. It was a time when marginalized communities, particularly African-Americans, were actively striving for civil rights, which strongly resonated with the EEJ movement's objectives (Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005; Ludwig, 2023).

As the civil rights movement progressed in its quest for racial equity and the dismantling of discriminatory systems, it served as a source of inspiration and shared principles for the emerging EEJ movement (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). The civil rights struggle set forth the strategies of grassroots activism, legal action, and community organization, strategies that the EEJ movement would later embrace (Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). It also emphasized the significance of solidarity among diverse marginalized groups and the necessity of addressing systemic injustices on multiple fronts.

The historical influence of the civil rights movement on the EEJ movement cannot be understated. The legacy of this alignment lives on in the ongoing pursuit of justice, equity, and the fair distribution of environmental resources and protection (Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). The evolution of the EEJ movement reflects not only its origins but also the broader historical and social context in which it emerged, where the fight for civil rights and the fight for environmental justice became interconnected in the pursuit of a more just and equitable society (Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005).

Since its inception in the late 1970s, the EEJ movement has remained committed to addressing environmental inequalities. It has extended its focus beyond the Love Canal incident and now encompasses a wide range of environmental and social justice issues (Gauna and Foster, 2003). The EEJ movement has achieved significant milestones, including advocacy for policy changes and regulations to reduce environmental health disparities (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). It has empowered affected communities to participate in decision-making and hold polluting industries accountable, raised public awareness about EEJ issues, conducted research to highlight environmental health disparities, expanded its impact globally, achieved legal victories, and contributed to improvements in environmental health standards, waste disposal practices, and overall environmental quality in affected communities (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mohai, 2009; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005).

As the movement gained momentum through the 1980s, it transitioned from localized concerns to a broader, more inclusive perspective, encompassing gendered impacts and gender inequality. Gendered impact in terms of environmental justice refers to the differential effects of environmental issues on individuals based on gender (Unger, 2006; Bennett, 2021; Parsons, 2021). This gendered approach highlights the power of women in addressing environmental issues and their role in challenging the skewed value system that prioritizes financial gain over morality (Unger, 2006; Bennett, 2021; Parsons, 2021). For example, women's limited access to

resources and decision-making power can hinder their ability to adopt sustainable practices (Unger, 2006).

The EJ movement significantly transformed during the pivotal 1991 National People of Color Environmental Leadership Summit. Before this landmark event, the EJ movement had primarily focused on addressing health hazards associated with toxic waste sites and responding to immediate threats to human health in marginalized communities. The framework called 'The Seventeen Principles of Environmental Justice'²² that emerged from the Summit represented a substantial shift in perspective (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). It expanded the movement's scope to encompass a broader range of EEJ issues, recognizing that environmental injustices extended beyond health hazards to affect various aspects of people's lives, including access to clean air and water, housing, and employment. This broader view acknowledged the complex interplay between social, gender, economic, and environmental factors in shaping the environmental landscape.

Additionally, the framework recognized that environmental health disparities and injustices affected a wide range of communities, transcending the confines of specific neighborhoods and the importance of engaging people of color across the board (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow; 2005). Consequently, the EJ framework promoted inclusivity by emphasizing the involvement of stakeholders from diverse backgrounds and communities (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow; 2005). The 'Seventeen Principles of Environmental Justice' framework was outlined by the text, which provided a comprehensive approach to address various dimensions of social and environmental equity ([First National People of Color Environmental Leadership](#), 1991; Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow; 2005). The framework considered factors like race, income, gender, sexual orientation, religion, and disability, recognizing the intersectionality of these factors in determining one's exposure to environmental hazards and ability to influence environmental decision-making (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow; 2005). This multi-dimensional approach represented a profound shift in the EJ movement, emphasizing the intricate web of social, economic, and environmental health disparities (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow; 2005).

Following the 1991 summit, the EJ movement continued to evolve (Gauna & Foster, 2003; Bullard, 2001). It broadened its focus, exploring how various individuals and stakeholder groups perceived and experienced environmental trade-offs, going beyond purely material and

²² At the People of Color Environmental Leadership Summit, a collective declaration was made to establish a movement uniting people of color nationally and globally. The principles outlined in this statement emphasize the reconnection to Mother Earth, cultural diversity, environmental justice, sustainable economic alternatives, and the pursuit of political, economic, and cultural liberation after centuries of colonization and oppression. ([First National People of Color Environmental Leadership](#), 1991)

economic considerations (Agyeman & Bullard, 2001). This pivotal moment laid the groundwork for the [EJ Executive Order 12898](#) in 1994. This broader perspective emphasized the significance of incorporating decision-making processes and acknowledging cultural differences when addressing equity and justice in ecosystem governance. The EJ movement, thus, transitioned from a local response to specific environmental injustices to a national and global campaign for broader environmental and social justice, addressing not only disparities in environmental quality but also the complex and culturally diverse aspects of these challenges.

In the years following the 1991 Summit, the EEJ movement continued to evolve and broaden its scope. It expanded to explore how various individuals and stakeholder groups perceived and experienced environmental trade-offs, delving beyond purely material and economic considerations. The movement gained significant momentum through the 1990s and early 2000s, embracing new issues, concerns, and campaigns, often led by grassroots organizations and activists (Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). These included movements such as the Flint Water Crisis²³, the Standing Rock protests²⁴, and initiatives that integrated environmental justice concerns into broader social justice movements like Black Lives Matter²⁵ (Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005). Youth-led campaigns, such as Fridays for Future and the Sunrise Movement, also emerged as powerful voices advocating for climate justice (Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018). Fridays for Future is an international movement that began by skipping schools on Fridays to protest outside the Swedish parliament building to call for stronger action on climate change, which has reverberated throughout the world (Fridays for Future, 2023). The Sunrise Movement is an organization that fights for the end of the climate crisis by pushing for the end of fossil fuel elites and for the Green New Deal, which is a congressional resolution for tackling climate change (The Sunrise Movement, 2023).

In addition to the significant advancements in gender and environmental justice within the EEJ movement, the unique challenges faced by Indigenous people, particularly Indigenous women and Indigenous gender minorities, are significant. Recent research in various environmental fields, including Indigenous-led biodiversity conservation and climate change adaptation projects, has shed light on the disparities experienced by Indigenous individuals of different genders (Parsons, 2021; Low, 2020; Njieassam, 2019; Vinyeta, 2016). Indigenous women and gender minorities often encounter unequal opportunities to access environmental

²³ The Flint water crisis began in 2014 when the source of drinking water for Flint, Michigan was switched to the Flint River. The river water was not properly treated, leading to lead contamination in the city's water supply. The crisis drew national attention and highlighted the disproportionate impact of environmental hazards on marginalized communities, particularly low-income and predominantly African American residents ([Erickson, 2019](#)).

²⁴ The Standing Rock protests were a series of demonstrations against the construction of the Dakota Access Pipeline near the Standing Rock Sioux Reservation in North Dakota. The protests, led by Indigenous activists, aimed to protect their land and water resources from potential environmental damage. The movement raised awareness about Indigenous rights and the environmental impact of infrastructure projects ([Guha, 2023](#)).

²⁵ The Black Lives Matter movement has expanded its focus to include an environmental justice initiative. It highlights the intersection of racial injustice and environmental issues, addressing topics such as air pollution, access to clean water, and climate change in predominantly Black communities ([BLM, 2023](#)).

resources and are disproportionately exposed to environmental threats (Parsons, 2021; Low, 2020; Njieassam, 2019; Vinyeta, 2016). Their ability to participate in decision-making processes related to environmental governance and management was also hindered, primarily due to patriarchal gender structures within Indigenous communities (Parsons, 2021; Low, 2020; Njieassam, 2019; Vinyeta, 2016). This results in the privilege of Indigenous male voices over those of Indigenous females and gender minorities in forums such as public consultations and tribal meetings (Parsons, 2021; Njieassam, 2019;). The intersection of gender, ethnicity, and environmental justice remains a critical focus, underscoring the multifaceted nature of disparities that persist in EEJ initiatives.

The expansion of the EEJ movement has increased its recognition of the importance of incorporating Indigenous perspectives and addressing the unique challenges faced by Indigenous communities, especially Indigenous women and gender minorities (Bullard & Agyeman, 2002; Bullard, 2001; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Mohai, 1992; Mullin, 2020; Pellow, 2018; Pellow, 2005; Parsons, 2021; Unger, 2006; Blackburn, 2023). This growing awareness reflects the movement's dedication to equity, inclusivity, and the pursuit of EJ for all marginalized populations. The EEJ movement continues to evolve, embracing intersectionality as a fundamental aspect of its mission and advocating for policies and practices that address the cumulative impacts of environmental hazards on historically disadvantaged communities, including Indigenous populations. The resilience and adaptability of the EEJ movement are evident in its ongoing commitment to advancing environmental justice and its responsiveness to different communities' specific needs and experiences from 1991 to the present day.

Strategies for Promoting Equitable Ocean Access and MPA Design

The intersection of EEJ and MPAs brings to light critical questions surrounding equitable benefits in marine conservation efforts. While MPAs serve the primary purpose of preserving biodiversity and enhancing ecosystem health, their establishment and management may inadvertently perpetuate environmental injustices (Jones, 2009; De Santo, 2013; Mascia, 2010; Garcia, 2017). Indigenous and underrepresented communities have, in certain instances, faced marginalization during the decision-making processes related to MPAs (Bennett, 2023; De Santo, 2013; Garcia, 2018; Parsons, 2021). Historical injustices, such as land dispossession and colonization, have left Indigenous communities socio-economically disadvantaged, hindering their effective participation in MPA decision-making (Jones, 2009; Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021). Systemic racism within decision-making structures further exacerbates the marginalization of these communities, limiting their involvement and influence in MPA designations (Bennett, 2023; Crellin, 2022; Rowland-Shea, 2020; Mohai, 1992; Stokdasla, 2012; Garcia, 2017). The dominance of economic interests during MPA decision-making can exacerbate gendered impacts and diminish the rights and interests of Indigenous and underrepresented communities (Mascia, 2010; Parsons, 2021).

To address these issues and promote more equitable access to coastal spaces and marine conservation benefits, several strategies can be considered. First, efforts should be made to

promote inclusive and equitable decision-making processes for MPA establishment and management. Indigenous and underrepresented communities must be provided with a voice in decision-making bodies to ensure that their interests are represented (Jones, 2009; Parsons, 2021). Engaging with these communities from the early stages of MPA planning is crucial to understanding their unique needs, perspectives, and traditional ecological knowledge (De Santo, 2013). This engagement can lead to more comprehensive MPA design and management, taking into account the specific circumstances and concerns of these communities.

Addressing historical injustices, such as land dispossession and colonization, should be a priority in MPA decision-making. Acknowledging and rectifying past wrongs through policies and actions that empower affected communities can help promote a sense of justice and inclusivity (Jones, 2009). Moreover, efforts should be made to eliminate discriminatory practices related to systemic racism within decision-making structures. By raising awareness of these issues and working to eradicate such practices, decision-making bodies can become more inclusive and representative of diverse communities (Bennett, 2023; Parsons, 2021).

Gender equality should also be a central consideration in MPA decision-making. Ensuring that the concerns and needs of women and gender-diverse individuals in Indigenous and underrepresented communities are given equal consideration can help mitigate gendered impacts and promote a more just and inclusive approach (Parsons, 2021). Capacity-building initiatives should be established to empower Indigenous and underrepresented communities. This can involve providing training in environmental management, conservation, and MPA stewardship to enable active participation and benefit from conservation efforts (Jones, 2009; Mascia, 2010; Garcia, 2017; Bennett, 2023). These initiatives should focus on building the skills and knowledge necessary for effective engagement in MPA-related activities and decision-making. It is essential to ensure that data related to MPAs is transparent and includes information on the distribution of benefits and any disparities. This data can be used to inform decision-making and track progress in addressing issues of equity and justice.

Finally, promoting collaborative governance models that involve multiple stakeholders and decision-making bodies can address the complexities of MPA establishment and management. Engaging a diverse array of perspectives and interests can lead to more well-rounded and equitable outcomes (Jones, 2009; Mascia, 2010; Garcia, 2017; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2022; Bennett, 2018; Floyd, 1999; Scott, 2013).

In addition to these strategies, enhancing the accessibility of coastal spaces and MPAs is crucial. This can be achieved by improving infrastructure, making beach parking, amenities, and overnight accommodations more affordable, and hosting community-specific events. Adding more lighting at beaches can enhance safety and encourage evening visits, making coastal spaces more accessible to all. Making amenities and accommodations more affordable can reduce financial barriers and increase access for underrepresented communities. Hosting community-specific events, such as surfing schools tailored to brown children, can promote inclusivity and provide opportunities for cultural and recreational engagement. For example,

organizations like Brown Girl Surf and The Sea League have demonstrated the positive impact of hosting community-specific events (Brown Girl Surf, 2023; The Sea League, 2023).

By implementing these strategies and enhancing accessibility, marine conservation efforts can become more equitable, just, and inclusive, ensuring that the benefits of conservation are shared more broadly among all communities, particularly those that have historically been underrepresented.

Recommendations for Next Steps

To address the challenges and harness the opportunities in EEJ, several recommendations should be considered:

- 1. Enhancing Coastal Safety Measures and Accessibility:** To address concerns about safety and the fear of crime in coastal areas, it is essential to implement strategies that enhance safety and comfort for all beachgoers (Bennett, 2023). This includes increasing lighting along coastal areas, especially in the evenings, to provide well-lit and safe environments. A couple of ideas include installing an alarm system along coastal areas, building charging stations for phones, and having lifeguards become a requirement at beaches. It is highly recommended that there are more signs in coastal areas that are translated into other languages, including but not limited to Spanish, Chinese, Braille, Vietnamese, and so on. It is recommended to prioritize a comprehensive examination and a steadfast commitment to dismantling systemic barriers, with the aim of fostering a more inclusive and equitable environment for all beachgoers and surfers, regardless of their racial background. This involves implementing policies, initiatives, and educational programs that actively address the existing disparities in coastal access and recreational opportunities, ensuring that all individuals can enjoy these natural spaces without facing systemic obstacles based on their race, ethnicity, sexual preference, or disability.
- 2. Promoting Inclusivity Through Community Engagement:** Hosting more events and programs aimed at encouraging participation from minority communities is the right step in promoting equitable access to coastal resources. These events should be designed to be inclusive and representative. Collaboration with local community leaders and organizations can help plan events that cater to the unique needs and preferences of different demographic groups, fostering a sense of belonging and involvement (Bennett, 2022; Stodoskla, 2018; Garcia, 2013; Garcia, 2017). Organizations like Outdoor Afro (Outdoorafro.org), and Brown Girl Surf (browngirlsurf.com), which celebrate and inspire Black and Brown connections and leadership in nature, offer valuable models for engaging minority communities with outdoor education, recreation, and conservation. Similarly, GreenLatinos (GreenLatinos.org), with an active community of Latino/a/x, draws strength from cultural power to demand equity, dismantle racism, and achieve victories in climate justice. Initiatives like Outdoor Afro, Brown Girl Surf, and Green Latinos contribute to the broader mission of fostering diverse and inclusive outdoor

experiences. In addition to these highlighted organizations, countless others share a commitment to fostering diverse and inclusive outdoor experiences. Recognizing the wealth of expertise and perspectives within these groups is a step forward in amplifying their voices and providing platforms that empower them to contribute meaningfully to the ongoing dialogue on equitable access to coastal resources.

3. **Affordable Coastal Accommodations:** Making parking and hotel accommodations more affordable for economically disadvantaged people in coastal regions, especially in states like California with high tourist demand, can significantly contribute to equitable access. By implementing pricing policies that consider the financial constraints of various income groups, it is possible to ensure that all individuals and families have the opportunity to enjoy the coast without being burdened by high costs. Strategies like affordable parking rates and subsidized accommodations can help make coastal visits more accessible while meeting the preferences of visitors who, on average, are willing to pay under \$10 a day for parking (Christensen & King, 2017; Bennett, 2023; Floyd, 1998; Stodolska, 2012). It is worth noting that such user fees, including parking and day-use fees, can serve as a vital part of the revenue stream that supports parks in California (Christensen & King, 2017). These fees contribute to the enhancement of amenities that enrich visitors' experiences along the coast, making them an integral part of ensuring long-term access and sustainability.
4. **Comprehensive State-Level Analysis:** A thorough examination of EEJ policies and definitions across all U.S. states is essential to understand variations and commonalities. As part of this broader examination, the 'Equity in California Ocean Access and Management Project' (www.californiaoceanaccessandmpas.com) serves as a noteworthy initiative. This project seeks to illuminate the dynamics of how California individuals from disadvantaged and severely disadvantaged communities, as defined by the U.S. Census, as well as Tribal communities, access, use, relate to and value the ocean. A key aspect of the investigation involves assessing the role of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in either amplifying or diminishing these benefits for people across diverse demographics, locations, and user groups as climate change unfolds. The research collective behind this project (<https://www.californiaoceanaccessandmpas.com/>) intends to conduct interviews, administer surveys, and hold focus group discussions in central and southern California between 2023-2025. The ultimate goal of this concerted effort is the co-development of local strategies aimed at enhancing equity in ocean access and MPA management, particularly in the context of a changing climate. By examining and learning from such projects, one can glean valuable insights into effective strategies for promoting environmental justice at both local and state levels.
5. **Equity Plans and Community Engagement:** Encouraging more federal and state agencies to develop Equity Plans and emphasizing community engagement in EEJ policy and decision-making processes is vital. These plans can serve as models for integrating environmental justice into various agency missions and actions.

6. **Environmental Education and Awareness:** Promoting environmental education and awareness, particularly among marginalized communities, is critical to empower individuals to participate actively in EEJ initiatives. This includes educating communities about their rights, the environmental issues they face, and how to engage in decision-making processes (Garcia, 2018; Rowland-Shea, 2020). And to have translations of other languages at the events too.
7. **Intersectionality and Inclusivity:** EEJ efforts should emphasize intersectionality by considering how various aspects of a person's identity, such as race, gender, disability, income, and location, intersect to influence their exposure to environmental hazards and access to resources. It is essential that EEJ definitions and principles evolve to encompass equitable access to nature and resources. Inclusivity should remain a core principle in EEJ to ensure all voices are heard and respected (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Scott, 2013; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Garcia, 2013). Addressing the barriers to equitable access to nature and resources should be embedded within the very definition of EEJ, highlighting the importance of removing socio-economic and systemic obstacles that limit the enjoyment of coastal regions, natural environments, and marine resources. (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2023; Bennett, 2018; Scott, 2013; Gauna & Foster, 2003; Garcia, 2013).
8. **Research on 21-Year Gap:** Future research should investigate the reasons for the 21-year gap in federal EEJ policy, examining the political, economic, and social factors that influenced policy priorities during that period. This understanding will help prepare for future policy interruptions and advocate for continuous attention to EEJ.

In conclusion, these recommendations provide a comprehensive roadmap for advancing EEJ in coastal areas and marine environments. By focusing on enhancing safety measures, promoting inclusivity through community engagement and accessibility, and making coastal accommodations more affordable, we can encourage individuals from all backgrounds to have equitable access to these natural resources. Conducting comprehensive state-level analyses, emphasizing environmental education and awareness, and incorporating the principles of intersectionality and inclusivity into EEJ definitions are crucial steps in the journey toward greater environmental justice. Exploring the reasons behind the 21-year gap in federal EEJ policy allows us to understand better and address policy interruptions. Through these actions, we can collectively work towards more accessible, safe, and equitable coastal regions and marine resources, promoting a more sustainable and just future for all.

Conclusion

The exploration of EEJ has unveiled a multifaceted landscape shaped by principles, challenges, and shifting policies aimed at ensuring equitable access to resources and safeguarding communities from environmental hazards. Our overview has examined the core dimensions of EEJ, including distributive justice, procedural justice, and recognitional justice,

which form the bedrock for addressing environmental health disparities (Bullard, 2001; Bennett, 2018; Gauna & Foster, 2003). These principles revolve around fair resource distribution, inclusive decision-making processes, and acknowledging the intrinsic worth of all communities.

In the context of our extensive oceans, a recurring theme emerges—Blue Justice (Parsons, 2021; Bennett, 2023; Dawson, 2018). This often-overlooked facet of EEJ emphasizes the significance of ensuring historically marginalized coastal communities can access marine opportunities while being shielded from environmental harm. With oceans covering over 70% of Earth's surface, disparities in access and benefits emphasize the importance of incorporating Blue Justice into the EEJ discourse in the 21st century.

Our examination of governance and policymaking has revealed policy shifts over time through various Federal and State Executive Orders (Appendix 1). These orders have embraced a broader interpretation of EEJ, incorporating climate justice principles rather than equitable access to nature and its resources, including oceans. A notable 21-year policy gap from 2000 to 2021 beckons further exploration into the factors that contributed to this hiatus (Appendix 1). The resurgence of EEJ policies since 2021 offers an opportunity for a deeper dive into the reasons behind this renewed emphasis.

It is imperative for the policy language to consider the diverse needs and interests of minority communities in the design of outdoor recreation and park access initiatives. By enhancing safety measures, promoting community engagement, and offering affordable coastal accommodations, we can work toward ensuring that individuals from all backgrounds have equitable access to these resources. Easing the economic disparities that limit access to publicly funded park and recreation resources is pivotal. It highlights the need to address these inequalities to provide better opportunities for economically disadvantaged Americans.

Federal and state agencies governing natural resources and oceans have also emphasized EEJ principles, prioritizing inclusivity, equitable protection, and meaningful community involvement (Appendix 2). These agencies, with varying missions, share a common commitment to equitable protection against environmental hazards and access to a healthy environment. However, their definitions differ in scope and community interpretations, reflecting their unique roles and responsibilities within EEJ (Appendix 2). The release of Equity plans by certain state-level agencies demonstrates a commitment to addressing environmental injustices (Appendix 2). Extensive research on EEJ commitments across state agencies could provide valuable insights into state-level EEJ landscapes (Appendix 3).

In conclusion, the future of EEJ is marked by both challenges and opportunities. The expansion of EEJ to encompass blue justice and equitable access to nature reflects a growing awareness of the interplay between environmental disparities and climate change. Comprehensive state-level analysis and the development of Equity plans can further EEJ goals. Environmental education, with a focus on intersectionality, promoting inclusivity through community engagement, and making coastal accommodations more affordable, can empower communities to engage in EEJ initiatives. The pursuit of EEJ represents a collective endeavor aimed at fostering a world where the distribution of environmental benefits is equitable and

environmental burdens are shared justly while acknowledging the intrinsic worth of all individuals and the interconnectedness of our planet. This vision is a call to continued diligence and exploration by communities, scholars, policymakers, and advocates in the years ahead.

APPENDIX 1

Table 1: Federal and State of California Executive Orders containing Environmental Justice Definitions

Level of Governance	Executive Order	Executive Order Name	Year	Definition
Federal	Executive Order 12898	“Address Environmental Justice in Minority Populations and Low-income Populations”	1994	"Each Federal agency shall make achieving environmental justice part of its mission by identifying and addressing, as appropriate, disproportionately high and adverse human health or environmental effects of its programs, policies, and activities on minority populations and low-income populations in the United States and its territories and possessions, the District of Columbia, the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, and the Commonwealth of the Mariana Islands."
Federal	Executive Order 13175	Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments	2000	"To reaffirm the fundamental principles of the United States Government-to-Government relationship with Indian tribes, to provide for meaningful and timely input by tribal officials in the development of regulatory policies that have tribal implications, and to strengthen the United States Government's accountability to Indian tribes."
Federal	Executive Order 13985	“Advancing Racial Equity and Support for Underserved Communities Through	2021	"It is the policy of my Administration to advance equity for all, including people of color and others who have been historically underserved, marginalized, and adversely affected by persistent poverty and inequality."

		Federal Government”		
Federal	Executive Order 14008	“Tackling the Climate Crisis at Home and Abroad”	2021	"Agencies shall make achieving environmental justice part of their missions by developing programs, policies, and activities to address the disproportionately high and adverse human health, environmental, climate-related, and other cumulative impacts on disadvantaged communities, as well as the accompanying economic challenges of such impacts.".
State (California)	Executive Order N-16-22	“California for all”	2022	“agencies and departments within my Administration can and should take additional actions to embed explicit analysis of equity considerations in policies and practices, including by analyzing demographic and geographic gaps in outcomes and access to funding and services, developing and consistently utilizing data analysis tools and practices to understand gaps in access to services and programs or outcomes from state programs, and reviewing community engagement strategies with a focus on Californians who reside in communities that have historically been underserved and marginalized;”
Federal	Executive Order 14091	“Further Advancing Racial Equity and Support for Underserved Communities Through the Federal Government”	2023	“The equitable treatment of all individuals and communities, particularly those who have historically been underserved or disadvantaged, in matters related to environmental policies, programs, and the fair distribution of environmental benefits and burdens. Environmental justice aims to rectify and prevent the disproportionate impact of environmental hazards, pollution, and resource allocation on marginalized and vulnerable populations. It seeks to ensure that everyone, regardless of their race, socioeconomic status, or geographic location, has the same level of protection from environmental harm and the opportunity to participate in decisions affecting their environment.”
Federal	Executive Order 14096	“Revitalizing Our Nation’s Commitment to Environmental Justice for All”	2023	"Environmental justice means the just treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of income, race, color, national origin, Tribal affiliation, or disability, in agency decision-making and other Federal activities that affect human health and the environment so that people are fully protected from disproportionate and adverse human health and environmental effects (including risks) and hazards, including those related to climate change, the cumulative impacts of environmental and other burdens, and the legacy of racism or other structural or systemic barriers, and have equitable access to a healthy, sustainable, and resilient environment in which to live, play, work, learn, grow, worship, and engage in cultural and subsistence practices."

APPENDIX 2

Table 2: Federal Agencies' Environmental Justice Definitions, Focusing on agencies that deal with pollution, oceans, and natural resources.

Level of Governance	Agency	Year	Definition	Source
Federal	Department of Interior (DOI)	2023	"To provide outstanding management of the natural and cultural resources entrusted to us in a manner that is sustainable, equitable, accessible, and inclusive of all populations."	Environmental Justice U.S. Department of the Interior (doi.gov)
Federal	Department of Commerce (DOC)	2021	"The Department has a longstanding role in the creation of jobs that will sustain economic growth, the stewardship of environmental data, the protection of life and property from environmental hazards and in predicting changes in climate, weather, oceans, and coasts, and conserving and managing coastal and marine ecosystems and resources. This traditional role is now augmented by a whole of-government approach focused on providing communities and businesses with the information, products, and services they need to prepare for, adapt, and prosper in a changing environment."	Strategic Plan U.S. Department of Commerce

Federal	Department of Agriculture (USDA)	1997	“ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE means that, to the greatest extent practicable and permitted by law, all populations are provided the opportunity to comment before decisions are rendered on, are allowed to share in the benefits of, are not excluded from, and are not affected in a disproportionately high and adverse manner by, government programs and activities affecting human health or the environment. “	USDA Departmental Regulation 5600-002
Federal Agency	Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)	1992	"The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations and policies."	Environmental Justice US EPA
Federal Agency within U.S. Department of Interior	U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service (USFWS)	2021	"To ensure fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all in the environmental arena. Environmental Justice communities define the environment as 'where we live, work, play, learn, and pray.'"	Environmental Justice About Us U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service (fws.gov)
Federal agency within the U.S. Department of Commerce	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	2023	"The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of race, color, gender, sexual orientation, national origin, tribal affiliation, religion, disability, or income during the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies,	NOAA Fisheries, Equity and Environmental Justice Strategy

			including but not limited to: 1) Equitable protection from environmental and health hazards; 2) Equitable access to a healthy, sustainable, and resilient environment in which to live, play, work, learn, grow, worship, and engage in cultural and subsistence practices; and 3) Equitable opportunity and access to decision-making processes for underserved communities."	
Federal Agency within the U.S. Department of Interior	Bureau of Land Management (BLM)	2022	"EJ is about more than addressing the harmful effects on humans from air pollution, toxic chemicals, groundwater pollution, or herbicides. EJ is also about ecological, economic, cultural, and social impacts—for instance, recreation opportunities of low-income and minority populations or communities, and their access to vital natural resources."	RGFO Scoping Handout - Env. Justice formatted.pdf (blm.gov)
Federal Agency within the U.S. Department of Interior	National Park Service (NPS)	2023	"To provide outstanding management of the natural and cultural resources entrusted to us in a manner that is sustainable, equitable, accessible, and inclusive of all populations."	NPS Groundwork Partnership Report
Federal Agency within the U.S.	U.S. Forest Service (USFS)	1997	"the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin, or income with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of	USDA Deputy Under Secretary promotes environmental justice goals US Forest Service

Department of Agriculture			environmental laws, regulations, and policies. It will be achieved when everyone enjoys the same degree of protection and equal access to the decision-making process to have a healthy environment in which to live, learn, and work."	
Federal Branch of Agency under NOAA	National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS)	2021	"Environmental justice is measured at the community level, where a community is either a group of individuals living in geographic proximity to one another or a set of individuals (such as migrant workers or Native Americans), where either type of group experiences common conditions of environmental exposure or effect."	NOAA Fisheries, Equity and Environmental Justice Strategy
Branch of Agency Under NOAA	Office of National Marine Sanctuaries (ONMS)	2023	"The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of race, color, gender, sexual orientation, national origin, tribal affiliation, religion, disability, or income during the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies, including but not limited to: 1) Equitable protection from environmental and health hazards; 2) Equitable access to a healthy, sustainable, and resilient environment in which to live, play, work, learn, grow, worship, and engage in cultural and subsistence practices; and 3) Equitable opportunity and access to decision-making processes for underserved communities."	NOAA Fisheries, Equity and Environmental Justice Strategy

<p>Federal Branch of Agency under NOAA</p>	<p>Channel Islands National Marine Sanctuary</p>	<p>2023</p>	<p>"The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of race, color, gender, sexual orientation, national origin, tribal affiliation, religion, disability, or income during the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies, including but not limited to: 1) Equitable protection from environmental and health hazards; 2) Equitable access to a healthy, sustainable, and resilient environment in which to live, play, work, learn, grow, worship, and engage in cultural and subsistence practices; and 3) Equitable opportunity and access to decision-making processes for underserved communities."</p>	<p>NOAA Fisheries, Equity and Environmental Justice Strategy</p>
<p>Federal Agency within U.S. Department of Interior</p>	<p>Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM)</p>	<p>2021</p>	<p>"BOEM defines environmental justice as the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people—regardless of race, color, national origin, or income—with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies."</p>	<p>Environmental Justice Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (boem.gov)</p>
<p>Federal level committee with a mandate to coordinate and integrate federal actions related to</p>	<p>White House's Ocean Policy Committee (OPC)</p>	<p>2023</p>	<p>"Based on Executive Order 14096's definition of "environmental justice," "ocean justice" refers to the just treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of income, race, color, national origin, Tribal affiliation, or disability, in Federal Agency decision-making and other Federal activities related to</p>	<p>Ocean Justice Strategy and Ocean Climate Action Plan</p>

ocean policy and science		the ocean. Advancing ocean justice will enable people to have protection from disproportionate and adverse human health and ocean environmental risks and hazards, as well as equitable access to the benefits of a healthy, sustainable, and resilient ocean environment in which to live, play, work, learn, grow, worship, and engage in cultural and subsistence practices. "	
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APPENDIX 3

Table 3: California Natural Resource Agencies' Environmental Justice Definitions

Agency	Year	Definition	Source
California Natural Resources Agency	2018	"California law defines Environmental Justice as "the fair treatment of people of all races, cultures and income with respect to the development, adoption, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies" (Government Code Section 65040.12 and Public Resources Code Section 72000)."	Environmental Justice Policy California Resources Agency
California State Lands Commission	2018	"Ensure that all voices are heard, all communities are treated fairly and equitably, and everyone is given equal opportunity to participate in the Commission's decision-making process, with an emphasis on ensuring that traditionally disadvantaged groups are not left behind"	Environmental Justice Policy (ca.gov)

California Department of Conservation	2018	“California law defines Environmental Justice as “the fair treatment of people of all races, cultures and income with respect to the development, adoption, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies” (Government Code Section 65040.12 and Public Resources Code Section 72000).”	Environmental Justice Policy California Resources Agency
California Fish and Wildlife of Commission	2021	“Environmental Justice looks to change that grim reality: to ensure fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all in the environmental arena. ”	Striving for Environmental Justice U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service (fws.gov)
California Ocean Protection Council (OPC)	2022	“The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of people of all races, cultures, incomes, and national origins, with respect to the development, adoption, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies.”	Equity Plan - Ocean Protection Council (ca.gov)
California Department of Fish & Wildlife (CDFW)	2022	“The fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people, regardless of their identity or circumstance, with respect to the development, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies. Fair treatment means that no population bears a disproportionate share of negative environmental consequences resulting from industrial, municipal, and commercial operations or from the execution of federal, state, and local laws; regulations, and policies. Meaningful involvement requires effective access to decision-makers for all, and the ability in all communities to make informed decisions and take positive actions to produce environmental justice for themselves.”	CDFW: Justice, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion: Definitions for Key terms
California Coastal Commission	2022	“Environmental justice” means the fair treatment of people of all races, cultures, and incomes with respect to the development, adoption, implementation, and enforcement of environmental laws, regulations, and policies.	Environmental Justice (ca.gov)

California Environmental Protection Agency	2023	“The principles of environmental justice call for fairness, regardless of race, color, national origin or income, and the meaningful involvement of community in the development of laws and regulations that affect every community’s natural surroundings, and the places people live, work, play and learn.”	Environmental Justice Program CalEPA
California Department of Water Resources (DWR)	2023	“Environmental Justice principles call for the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, color, national origin or income, in the development, adoption, implementation, and enforcement of all environmental laws, regulations, and policies that affect every community’s natural surroundings, and the places people live, work, play, and learn.”	Environmental Justice (ca.gov)
California State Parks	2023	“One of the core values at California State Parks is cultural diversity and accessibility. We believe in the right of all Californians, including persons with disabilities, to have access to recreational opportunities, and enjoy the cultural, historic, and natural resources found in our state parks.”	Accessible Parks for All (ca.gov)

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